

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

[Voltar](#)

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Data manipulation by Migration\]](#) ^{*} smell?

This code smell refers to modules that perform both data and structural changes in a database schema via *Ecto.Migration*. Migrations must be used exclusively to modify a database schema over time (e.g., by including or excluding columns and tables). When this responsibility is mixed with data manipulation code, the module becomes less cohesive, more difficult to test, and therefore more prone to bugs. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Splitting a large module\]](#): When a module that behaves like *Ecto.Migration* performs both data and structural changes in a database schema, it becomes less cohesive, more difficult to test, and therefore more prone to bugs. In these cases, we should split this module into two, moving only the attributes and functions related to data updates to the new module.
 2. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): In some cases, after splitting an original module into several smaller and more cohesive modules, the name of the original module can no longer make sense, providing an opportunity also to perform this refactoring.
 3. [\[Extract function\]](#): We can use this operation in the original module to create a new function responsible for calling the routines for altering the data in the database, now present in the new module.
 4. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): After extracting this function, we can use this refactoring to reposition it in the new module created after splitting the original module.
 5. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): Finally, we can eliminate the call to the extracted function in the original module to start the database alteration routines, as this function, now present in the new module, should only be called during the initialization of a *Mix.Task*.
- [\[Simplifying Ecto schema fields validation\]](#): Optionally, we can take the opportunity to apply this refactoring in the original module, making it less prone to errors during the validation of the database schema modified via *Ecto.Migration*.
 - [\[Pipeline for database transactions\]](#): Optionally, we can also take the opportunity to apply this operation in the new module created only to perform changes on data, thus improving its readability by using *Ecto.Multi*.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Shotgun Surgery\]](#) smell? *

This smell refers to a code with responsibilities spread across many Elixir modules, so that modifications require many small changes to many different modules at the same time. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactoring:

- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): When we need to simultaneously make a series of small changes in different modules, it's easy to overlook something important. In this case, you can use this refactoring to reorganize the modules, aiming to make them more cohesive so that all necessary changes are concentrated within their respective modules. If no current module seems like a good candidate to receive parts moved from others, we need to create one.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Dynamic atom creation\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function creates *atoms* in an uncontrolled and dynamic way, which can negatively affect memory management. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): We can replace a call to the function `String.to_atom/1` with an explicit conversion. To do this, we can use this refactoring on the calls to `String.to_atom/1`, creating a new function. This new function should take a *string* as a parameter and convert it to an *atom*. The body of this function should include a conditional to check the content of the *string*. Depending on its content, the function will return a different *atom* directly.
 2. [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): After extracting a new function for explicit conversions from *strings* to *atoms*, we can use this refactoring to transform the function into a multi-clause function, where each clause is responsible for returning one of the possible converted *atoms*.
- [\[Folding against a function definition\]](#): If there is already a function in the module responsible for performing the explicit conversion of a *string* to an *atom* (e.g., a function extracted for this purpose at a different point in the same module), we can replace a call to `String.to_atom/1` with a call to that function.
1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): Another alternative to refactor this code is to first duplicate the line where the function `String.to_atom/1` is called to create an *atom* dynamically. The new line should replace the call to `String.to_atom/1` with a call to `String.to_existing_atom/1`. This will ensure that string-to-atom conversions only map the *strings* to *atoms* already in memory. To enable this type of mapping, a suggestion is to create a *list* of these possible *atoms* within the function where this refactoring was applied.
 2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): After duplicating and modifying the duplicated line, we can eliminate the original line where the call to `String.to_atom/1` occurred.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Unrelated multi-clause function\]](#) smell? *

Using multi-clause functions in Elixir, to group functions of the same name, is not a code smell in itself. However, due to the great flexibility provided by this programming feature, some developers may abuse the number of guard clauses and pattern matches to group *unrelated* functionality. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): A possible solution to this smell is to use this refactoring to break up the business rules that are mixed into several different simple functions. Specifically, groups of clauses from the original function that share related functionalities can be renamed with an identical name, thus forming a new multi-clause function.
 2. [\[Function clauses to/from case clauses\]](#): Optionally, after renaming the groups of related clauses, thus creating new multi-clause functions, these multi-clause functions can be transformed into single-clause functions by mapping function clauses into clauses of case statements.
- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): When unrelated clauses of a multi-clause function differ to the point where they do not make sense in the current module, these clauses can be moved to other modules where they fit better, thus making the code more cohesive.
 - [\[Struct guard to matching\]](#): Optionally, when some of the clauses of a multi-clause function use a guard clause involving the functions *is_struct/1* or *is_struct/2*, we can use this refactoring to simplify the pattern matching performed by these function clause's signature.
 - [\[Equality guard to pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, when an unnecessary temporary variable is extracted from a *struct*'s field in a clause of a multi-clause function only to be used in an equality comparison in a guard, we can use this operation to simplify the pattern matching performed by this function clause's signature.
 - [\[Simplifying guard sequences\]](#): Optionally, when a clause of a multi-clause function contains redundant logical propositions, we can simplify the pattern matching performed by this function clause's signature through the transformation carried out by this refactoring.
 - [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): Optionally, when what differentiates the clauses of a multi-clause function are only the logical checks performed in their guard clauses, we can use this refactoring to replace all guards with traditional conditionals, creating only one clause for the function.
 - [\[Simplifying pattern matching with nested structs\]](#): Optionally, when using pattern matching to perform deep extraction in nested *structs* passed as parameters to a clause of a multi-clause function, we may create unnecessarily messy and hard-to-understand code. With this refactoring, we can simplify this kind of extraction by performing pattern matching only on the outermost *struct* in the nesting, instead of matching patterns with very internal *structs*.
 - [\[Remove unnecessary calls to length/1\]](#): Optionally, when unnecessary calls to the function *length/1* are used in guard clauses to differentiate the pattern matching performed by different clauses of a multi-clause function, we can replace these calls with direct pattern matching on the parameter list of the function clauses, thereby improving code efficiency.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Agent obsession\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when the responsibility for interacting with an Agent process is spread across the system. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Generalise a function definition\]](#): When functions responsible for directly interacting with the *Agent* are scattered throughout the system, it indicates the presence of this smell. We can refactor them simultaneously using this operation, centralizing the responsibility for interacting with the *Agent* in a single module or function.
 2. [\[Moving a definition\]](#): After generalizing the functions that were originally responsible for directly accessing the *Agent*, the generic function created to centralize this task might not be located in the most appropriate module. This refactoring can be used to address this issue.
 3. [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): Functions that were originally responsible for directly accessing the *Agent*, once generalized by the previous refactoring, may require the addition of new parameters to be passed to the generic function called within their bodies.
- [\[Behaviour extraction\]](#): One way to remove this smell is to define a *behaviour* containing a contract that specifies the format of all functions intended to interact with an *Agent* throughout the system. Following this refactoring, all modules that wish to access the *Agent* must implement this extracted *behaviour*.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Using App Configuration for libraries\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a library function is configured using parameterization mechanisms instead of arguments, thereby limiting its reuse by clients. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): When we have a library function that depends on globally defined values, which reduces its reusability, we can use this refactoring to add a new optional parameter of type *Keyword list* with a default value. This new parameter allows the function to be configured in different ways when called. If the optional parameter is not provided in the call, the function will continue to behave as originally, using the same global configurations.
2. [\[Typing parameters and return values\]](#): We can also use this refactoring to explicitly document the type of the added parameter (i.e., *Keyword list*).

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Complex extractions in clauses\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a function uses pattern matching in its signature to extract values that are used both in guard checks and in the function body. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Simplifying pattern matching with nested structs\]](#): When using pattern matching to perform deep extraction in nested *structs* passed as parameters to a clause of a multi-clause function, we may create unnecessarily messy and hard-to-understand code. With this refactoring, we can simplify this kind of extraction by performing pattern matching only on the outermost *struct* in the nesting, instead of matching patterns with very internal *structs*.
 - [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): To prevent complex extractions in clauses, which are used both to access data extracted in guard clauses and in the function body, from making the code confusing, we can use this refactoring to replace all guards with traditional conditionals, consolidating them into a single clause for the function. This way, all extracted data will be used exclusively in the function body.
 - [\[Equality guard to pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, if an unnecessary temporary variable is extracted from a *struct's* field in a clause of a multi-clause function and is only used for an equality comparison in a guard, this refactoring can simplify the pattern matching in that clause.
 - [\[Struct guard to matching\]](#): Optionally, if some clauses of a multi-clause function use guard clauses involving the functions *is_struct/1* or *is_struct/2*, this refactoring can simplify the pattern matching performed by these clauses.
 - [\[Remove unnecessary calls to length/1\]](#): If a list extraction is performed in a function clause only to use it in an unnecessary call to *length/1* in a guard clause, this extraction can be replaced by using pattern matching directly, eliminating the need for the guard clause. To do this, use this refactoring.
 - [\[Function clauses to/from case clauses\]](#): When complex extractions are done in clauses of multi-clause functions, making it difficult to understand which data is used inside or outside the function body, we can use this refactoring to transform a multi-clause function into a single clause function. By doing this, we will map the function's clauses into clauses of a case statement, ensuring that all extractions occur within the function body.
1. [\[Introduce a temporary duplicate definition\]](#): When we are moving an extraction performed in a function clause into its body, we can initially use this refactoring to duplicate within the function body an extraction performed in the signature.
 2. [\[Temporary variable elimination\]](#): After duplicating the complex extraction within the function body, we can use this operation to remove unnecessary extracted parts, thereby cleaning up the code.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Voltar

Avançar

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* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

[Voltar](#)

[Enviar](#)

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